

Microalgae production at industrial scale: modelling and control challenges*

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Abstract—The 21st century society faces significant sustainability challenges, including climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation. Microalgae have emerged as a versatile and sustainable solution to mitigate these problems. The microalgae production process involves harnessing their ability to convert sunlight, carbon dioxide, and nutrients (contaminants in wastewater media or agriculture effluents) into valuable biomass through photosynthesis, thus providing a synergy between biomass production and environmental remediation. When microalgae are produced, the culture conditions, including temperature, light intensity, nutrient concentration, dissolved oxygen, and pH, are critical factors that must be carefully controlled to ensure optimal microalgae growth. The growth dynamics of microalgae is influenced by a multitude of interacting factors that, together with the biological nature of microalgae and the variability of weather conditions, pose a significant barrier to the implementation of effective control algorithms. This tutorial paper summarizes the results of more than 20 years of experience working in the scale-up and development of modeling, control, and optimization methods for microalgae production systems. Theoretical and experimental results at industrial scale will be presented to show the potential of microalgae production systems and how control engineering solutions can contribute to make them more competitive in the market for bioproduct generation and wastewater regeneration.

I. INTRODUCTION

The depletion of valuable resources such as fossil fuels or clean water, the pollution of surface waters, or the emission of greenhouse gases as a result of the combustion of coal or oil are some of the main concerns of our current society. In this sense, numerous efforts are being made worldwide, trying to create campaigns to raise awareness in society about the costs, and environmental and economic impacts of these problems. Likewise, there are research lines dedicated to these issues to work on the development of new technologies that contribute to the reduction of environmental impact, CO₂ mitigation, waste transformation and recycling, wastewater treatment, and the development of alternative energy sources.

For years, bioprocess technology, or biotechnology, has developed as a promising field with the potential to significantly address the challenges mentioned above. Bioprocess operations use microbial metabolism, animal cells, plant

cells, and cellular components to produce new biotechnological products (animal feed, pharmaceuticals, biomass, biogas, biodiesel, etc.) and eliminate wastes such as CO₂ or other types of pollutants. Within the field of biotechnology, microalgae are one of the bioprocesses with the greatest potential in relation to the previously mentioned problems. Microalgae biomass has a high oil content, requires low water consumption and can be produced in arid lands, thus contributing to low waste generation and reduced consumption compared to other types of crops. Because of the protein properties and carbohydrate content of the resulting biomass, they can be used to obtain bioproducts such as biofertilizers, animal feed, human food and cosmetics, among others. On the other hand, these microorganisms have been shown to accumulate up to 70 % of their weight in lipids, which allows them to be transformed into biodiesel through the direct transesterification process [1], [2], [3]. In addition, they are an elegant solution for wastewater treatment due to their ability to utilize inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus for their growth [4], and recent studies have analyzed their combination with photo-Fenton processes to cope with pollutant removal [5], [6]. Furthermore, microalgae are primarily responsible for the mitigation and transformation of CO₂ into biomass on the planet, thus contributing to the reduction of the effect of global warming [7]. Due to this great potential, the production of microalgae has been postulated as an industrial process of great relevance worldwide, contributing directly to alleviate the aforementioned global pollution problems. This fact is corroborated by the continuous growth of the microalgae industry, with an annual increase of around 10% and with more than 57,000 tons of biomass generated worldwide [8]. Despite this potential of microalgae, energy-intensive processes such as photobioreactor operation and harvesting can offset their benefits. Optimizing operations, using renewable energy, and improving harvesting efficiency can significantly reduce the overall carbon footprint.

The industrial production of microalgae is a highly interesting and sustainable process, but its actual competitiveness is closely related to its optimization. The biological nature of the process hinders this task, mainly because of the high non-linearity of the process along with its changing nature, features that make its modeling, control, and optimization remarkably challenging.

From an engineering point of view, production systems in the field of biotechnology cannot be modeled and controlled like other types of industrial processes. Considerable adaptation effort is required to exploit the modeling and control knowledge and techniques commonly used in process

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control. It is important to note that due to the high complexity of these types of processes, joint and coordinated work between specialists in the fields of control engineering, chemical engineering, and biotechnology is necessary. It should be noted that the microalgae production process, in addition to having complex and nonlinear dynamics, incorporates non-stationary steady-state behavior, presence of changing perturbations, and strong interactions from the population level to the cell level through light attenuation [9]. Furthermore, microalgae are generally grown outdoors and therefore grow in conditions of permanent change and subject to daily variations in light and temperature.

The complexity of the microalgae production process is due to the strong influence of multiple variables on the photosynthesis rate, such as solar radiation, pH, dissolved oxygen, and culture temperature. The light requirements cannot be manipulated during a normal operating day and are determined by the structure of the reactor. Regarding the culture temperature, in the case of open reactors, it is also usually not controlled and is managed by design aspects (the associated cost has not justified its control so far). In the case of closed reactors, heat exchangers are sometimes used to achieve the desired temperature. On the other hand, pH and dissolved oxygen are two variables that can be controlled and have a strong dependence on the photosynthesis rate and therefore on biomass production. This is why mathematical models and the design of appropriate control strategies are required to capture the dynamics of the system and to keep these variables close to their optimal values. If this is not achieved, the growth of microalgae (which occurs on a slower time scale) could be considerably affected, causing a reduction in biomass production, and in some extreme cases may reach situations of detrimental damage to the microorganisms.

Until recently, there was a lack of dynamic models that could adequately describe and relate microalgae growth and biomass production phenomena to the rest of the process variables. As in any biological system, these types of processes are highly complex because of the presence of living organisms and the types of metabolic reactions that occur in these microorganisms. Microalgae are photosynthetic microorganisms with a high ability to store nutrients. Moreover, their pigments attenuate light, which is their energy source and generates a strong dependence between biological (microalgae growth) and physical (hydrodynamics and radiative transfer properties) phenomena. Finally, these organisms are so changeable that classical metabolic engineering results can rarely be applied. Due to all these properties, the vast majority of existing models in the literature describe these subprocesses separately [10], [11], or consider static balances considering the system as a classical mixing tank [12], [13], [14], [15]. In the last decade, great effort has been made in the development of dynamic models that combine all existing phenomena and consider the spatio-temporal distribution of the system variables [16], [17], [18], [19], [20]. Furthermore, data-driven models have also been obtained for some of the most relevant variables, such as pH [21], [22]. Another aspect

to highlight is that there are many variables important for optimization and control purposes for which there are no robust and reliable online sensors, and therefore cannot be measured in real time, such as biomass concentration or total inorganic carbon. In this field, there are some contributions with methods based on optical density measurements, cell count analysis, or dry matter measurements to estimate these variables [1], [23], [24], [25]. However, all of these methods generally provide discontinuous measurements and are impossible to use for online control objectives. This is why it is necessary to develop state observers for these variables [26], [27] or to develop new online sensors [28].

Regarding control strategies, the microalgae production control problem can be expressed as a hierarchical control problem with objectives at two different time scales. There are high-level objectives with slow time scales in which the objectives are to maximize biomass production, reduce production costs, and/or maximize water treatment capacity when microalgae are grown with wastewater. These long-term objectives also make use of climate and/or market predictions and generate as a result the optimal setpoints for the main process variables that have an impact on microalgae production, such as pH, dissolved oxygen, or culture temperature. On the other hand, the second layer of the hierarchical control problem involves the design of control strategies for these process variables to achieve the setpoints generated by the upper layer. These control problems are characterized by fast dynamics and are subject to permanent dynamic changes due to variability in climatic conditions, culture status, and/or nutrient availability.

Numerous works are available in the literature at laboratory scale [29], [30], [31] (where it is easier to achieve a controlled environment) and less at industrial scale in outdoor conditions. In the latter case, which is the one of interest in this work, there are relevant contributions for pH control, where it is possible to find all kinds of control strategies such as on/off control, which is the most widely used [32], [33], PID control [34], delay compensated control [35], model-based predictive control (MPC) [36], [37], [38], [39], event-based control [40], sliding mode control [41], learning MPC [42], nonlinear MPC [43], and data-driven adaptive controllers [22], [44], among others. In the case of dissolved oxygen, despite being another extremely important variable for microalgae growth, there are not many control strategies in the literature. Generally, in practice, air is usually added in excess to avoid reaching high values of dissolved oxygen, resulting in high energy consumption and yield losses [45], [46]. Thus, new control strategies based on PID control and event-driven control have recently been proposed to adequately control dissolved oxygen and improve this aspect [47], [48]. In addition, hierarchical control and real-time optimization strategies are being applied, oriented to optimize the dilution and medium injection processes in the reactor [49], [50], [51], as well as to maximize biomass production through hierarchical control strategies [29], [52], [53], which, as indicated, is the ultimate goal of this type of facility.

Finally, one of the current challenges in microalgae production is the detection of contamination in the culture. In particular, in an open environment, there is the risk that other undesirable genera of microalgae may colonize and compete with the species of interest. Contamination can have a significant impact on the quality and productivity of a culture, affecting both the expected results and the overall yield. It is therefore crucial to implement strict control and continuous monitoring of the culture environment to mitigate this problem. Currently, this process is carried out by manual analysis of samples under the visual inspection of an expert capable of discerning the morphological differences between genera using an optical microscope, which requires highly skilled workers. To facilitate this process, deep learning and machine learning techniques have been proposed solutions to contribute to microalgae classification and contamination detection [21], [54].

This tutorial first presents a general description of the microalgae, their properties, and their main production systems. Subsequently, the different main phenomena describing their dynamic behavior will be discussed and a set of first-principles models will be presented incorporating mass balances, transport phenomena, thermodynamic relationships, and biological behaviour. Likewise, some recent data-driven models will be described. Afterward, the existing control problems in this type of processes will be presented and representative control strategies for the main variables of the system will be described. Then, new models based on artificial intelligence algorithms will be presented for microalgae classification and contamination detection purposes. The models and control strategies presented in this work have been experimentally evaluated in industrial or semi-industrial scale photobioreactors at the facilities of the University of Almería and in cooperation with different companies of the microalgae sector.

II. MICROALGAE

Microalgae belong to the group of photosynthetic organisms, i.e. those that make use of solar energy to produce organic compounds. Specifically, they have the ability to convert solar energy and carbon sources, such as CO_2 , into biomass. Figure 1 provides a schematic description of their production mechanism. As can be seen, in addition to solar radiation, microalgae require nutrients for their growth, with carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus being essential. Carbon is supplied by injection of CO_2 , which in turn contributes to the regulation of the pH of the system. Nitrogen and phosphorus can be supplied in various soluble forms available in food production in agriculture, and this has been the usual form of supply in the microalgae production. However, due to the large amount of energy required to generate this type of fertilizer and the associated cost, nitrogen and phosphorus are currently being recovered from waste through the combined process of wastewater treatment or agriculture effluents with microalgae, thus contributing to provide a more environmentally sustainable solution while allowing the generation of large amounts of biomass [4]. Finally, as a result of

the photosynthesis process, organic matter is synthesized, leading to an increase in biomass concentration and oxygen release.

As stated in [2], the production of microalgae is a process that must be properly planned and carried out, where the main stages are the following: 1) preparation of the culture medium; 2) *biomass production in photobioreactors*; 3) biomass harvesting; 4) water treatment for recirculation or discharge; and 5) stabilization of biomass or its transformation into final products. Each of these stages plays a key role in the production process. However, the second stage concerning biomass production in photobioreactors is the most complex and relevant because of the large number of factors that affect the operation of the system and where process control plays a fundamental role in order to maximize production.

Fig. 1: Factors influencing microalgae growth

From a photosynthetic point of view, microalgae are very similar to plants, but have certain differences: they are microscopic, with a size between 2 and 20 μm ; they tend to occur in suspension in water and therefore do not require fertile soils for production; their growth rate is much higher than that of plants, with growth times of less than 1 day; their photosynthetic efficiency is much higher than that of plants because they lack roots or structures of high size; and they require the input of high amounts of nutrients to maximize their production [2].

Currently, there are more than 30,000 species of microalgae cataloged, but less than 100 have been studied and no more than 10 strains are used for commercial use [2]. The type of microalgae to be used depends on the purpose of the resulting biomass based on the contents of pigments, food, lipids, etc., or on its tolerance in wastewater treatment. For example, *Golenkinia*, *Chlorella*, *Spirulina*, *Ankistrodesmus*, *Euglena*, *Navicula*, *Chlamydomonas*, *Phormidium*, *Scenedesmus*, *Nitzschia* and *Stigeoclonium* species are considered suitable for wastewater treatment and their corresponding biomass production. Many of these species are also commercially interesting for human and/or animal food, the production of essential oils, and biofuels, among other purposes [2], [8], [55].

III. MICROALGAE PRODUCTION

Microalgae production is a process that depends on so many factors. The photobioreactor where microalgae are produced is a very important element because it determines the operating mode, the production costs, and the final product to be obtained. In addition, microalgae growth is

affected by many different variables, such as solar radiation, nutrients supply, culture temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen. Therefore, the influence and impact of these variables must be taken into account to achieve suitable microalgae production. Finally, an adequate scale-up process must be performed to properly produce and adapt pure microalgae from controlled indoor conditions in the lab to industrial outdoor conditions in open reactors. This section briefly summarizes all of these aspects.

A. Production systems

Microalgae production systems are commonly classified as closed or open reactors. Closed reactors are usually intended for the production of high-value microalgae biomass that is not very resistant to extreme conditions or that has high safety requirements during their growth. The key feature of these reactors is that they separate the culture from the environment, preventing the entry of external contaminants and achieving tighter control of their conditions. There are multiple types of closed reactors, such as bubbling columns or flat panels, but the most widespread are tubular photobioreactors, such as those shown in Figure 2. These are made up of a series of forced conducts through which the water containing the microalgae flows. The main drawbacks of these reactors are their higher energy consumption, higher installation and operation costs, and difficulty in scaling up.

Fig. 2: Tubular reactor located at IFAPA research center.

The alternative to closed reactors are open reactors, especially raceway reactors, such as the one shown in Figure 3. These consist of large, entirely open ponds in which the culture circulates in a cyclic fashion, collecting energy for photosynthesis from the sun. The simplicity of its design directly results in lower costs, both at the installation and operational level, which justifies it to be the most widely used option at the industrial level, producing more than 90% of the biomass of microalgae globally. They are also simpler to scale up and allow a larger volume of water to be treated if the process is intended to be used for wastewater treatment. However, the simplicity of these systems comes with some drawbacks. For one thing, the control of their conditions is far from trivial, since the culture is constantly exposed to the

environment. Moreover, they are highly susceptible to the entry of external contaminants. It is not unusual for the culture to be contaminated by another strain that ends up spreading. This creates a problem in assessing the composition of the culture for its use in downstream applications. On the other hand, the initial culture itself can mutate and evolve, often becoming more tolerant to extreme conditions and more resistant to unfavorable situations, which is a good thing from the point of view of process operation and control. For that reason, monitoring and supervision tools are required, as will be presented in Section VI.

Fig. 3: Raceway reactor located at IFAPA research center.

B. Factors influencing microalgae production

The most important variables influencing the growth rate of microalgae are solar radiation, nutrient supply, medium temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen. The most decisive factor is undoubtedly solar radiation, as it is the main source of energy for the production process. Microalgae, as photosynthetic organisms, make use of the 400-700 nm region of the solar spectrum (photosynthetically active radiation or PAR). However, microalgae are saturated with radiation values higher than $200 \mu E/m^2 s$, and can become photo-inhibited. They therefore present the problem that they cannot be exposed to direct solar radiation and solutions are required that allow the radiation to be distributed among as many cells as possible. This factor is determined by the design of the photobioreactor so that the light hitting its surface is attenuated according to the biomass concentration, the extinction coefficient, and the depth of the culture. Therefore, photobioreactors are designed to maximize light capture at the surface and at the same time optimize the culture depth to achieve adequate mixing and maintain the biomass concentration close to its optimal values.

In terms of nutrient supply, microalgae biomass is mainly composed of carbon (45%), nitrogen (7%), and phosphorus (1%), in addition to oxygen and hydrogen, which are obtained directly from water. In the case of carbon, it can be provided in the form of carbonate or bicarbonate, but CO_2 injections are used, as they contribute to its mitigation and, in turn, favor the regulation of the pH of the medium.

The fundamental reaction of photosynthesis indicates that up to 1.8 kg of CO₂ is required to produce 1 kg of biomass. With regard to nitrogen and phosphorus, as pointed out above, although these can be supplied by existing soluble compounds, they are currently recovered from wastewater or agriculture effluents and contribute to the water purification process. For these nutrients, approximately 0.1 kg of nitrogen and 0.01 kg of phosphorus are required to produce 1 kg of microalgae biomass.

Regarding temperature, most species grow in an optimal range of 20 to 30 °C. For each strain of microalgae, there are three temperatures to consider: a minimum temperature below which microalgae growth stops, an optimum temperature at which growth is at its maximum, and a maximum temperature above which growth is not possible and the culture dies. For this reason, if very high temperatures are reached for a continuous period of time, it would be necessary to have a cooling system that prevents overheating of the medium and thus prevents the collapse of the culture. Usually, industrial photobioreactors do not have temperature regulation systems due to the high costs involved in addition to the high energy consumption. Therefore, the determination of the range of temperature variation is achieved as part of the design of the reactor and its location, forcing the microalgae to perform their optimal growth at the average daily temperature values where the photobioreactor is located [56].

In the case of pH, as with temperature, there are minimum, maximum, and optimum values associated with each strain that delimit and determine the effect of this variable on the growth rate of microalgae. For the vast majority of microalgae, the optimal pH value is between 7 and 9. The pH can be controlled by adding acidic solutions to the medium, but, as discussed above, it is usually regulated by injection of CO₂, which is also used as a carbon source. The control of pH is one of the main problems in the microalgae production system, since a balance must be found between CO₂ consumption and the increase of biomass productivity [57]. All this also depends on the CO₂ source used, a factor that characterizes the type of control problem in question. CO₂ can be obtained from the atmosphere, supplied as a pure gas, or supplied from combustion gases. The first case is usually not considered in practice, as the carbon supply from CO₂ in the atmosphere is very limited, reaching only 5% of the carbon required by the culture [58]. The second case, where pure CO₂ is used, is the most effective as it is when the highest transfer is obtained. However, this option is the most expensive and requires adequate control strategies to efficiently supply CO₂. Finally, if economic aspects are considered, the use of CO₂ from flue gas is the most cost-effective and sustainable solution. In this case, it is very important to ensure a high transfer rate, which has been analyzed in detail in the literature and where control plays a fundamental role [40], [59], [60], [61].

Finally, dissolved oxygen is the last variable to be analyzed to consider its effect on the growth rate of microalgae. During the photosynthesis process, microalgae release oxygen, and

such oxygen production can be used as an indicator of microalgae growth in the system. However, such oxygen accumulates in the medium and needs to be removed; otherwise, it can cause adverse effects on microalgae. In fact, the vast majority of strains are inhibited by the accumulation of dissolved oxygen when its concentration is higher than 20 mg/L. Therefore, it is essential to have oxygen removal systems that prevent the maximum limit established for each strain from being reached. This aspect has been extensively studied in the literature, and in industrial systems, aeration systems are usually used to provide air flow and achieve reduction of dissolved oxygen in the medium [62].

C. Scale-up process

Scaling up microalgae production from lab conditions to industrial production takes between 1 and 2 months depending on the microalgae strain. It is a sensitive process where microalgae must switch between different growth states and move from indoor to outdoor conditions. It is a combination of consecutive batch-mode stages using different types of reactors until the system is in continuous mode in large-scale photobioreactors.

Fig. 4: Microalgae lab at IFAPA research center.

A brief example of the scale-up process using the facilities available in the agreement between the IFAPA research center and the University of Almería is presented in the following. In the first stage, microalgae are scaled up from 1 L to 10 L using bottles and controlled conditions in the lab, as shown in Figure 4. This stage is in batch mode and takes about 1 week. Light and temperature are constant, there is no control of pH, air is continuously injected to avoid high values of dissolved oxygen, and no nutrients are supplied. Afterward, the microalgae are moved outdoors to scale from 10 L up to 100 L using column reactors such as those shown in Figure 5. This process is in batch mode and takes between 1 and 2 weeks, as the microalgae must adapt from indoor to outdoor conditions. At this stage, pH is controlled using on/off control, constant aeration is used, and nutrients are supplied only at the beginning of the stage. Then, the next step is also in batch mode and consists of moving microalgae from the columns to the tubular reactors presented in Figure

Fig. 5: Column reactors at IFAPA research center.

2, where the scaling up is from 100 L up to 5000 L. This stage also takes between 1 and 2 weeks, pH and dissolved oxygen are controlled with on/off controllers, and nutrients are also supplied at the beginning. Finally, the microalgae are moved to the raceway reactors (see Figure 3) to finish the scale-up process from 5000 to 15000 or 30000 L (or even a larger volume) depending on the size of the final reactor. Since then, the system is in industrial production and is working in continuous mode. Note that the system can continue producing indefinitely if the maintenance of the reactor is adequate. In this stage, when the system works in continuous mode and on an industrial scale, the proposed modeling and control solutions presented in this tutorial are important to make the microalgae production system sustainable, profitable, and competitive in the market. It is important to note that although in this example the final production stage was described for raceway reactors, it could also be performed using tubular reactors, the previous stages being exactly the same as described before.

IV. MODELING

This section presents a set of models for the most common types of photobioreactors discussed above, tubular and raceway photobioreactors. Primarily, first-principles models are presented and then data-driven models used for control design purposes are also described. All models presented and cited have been calibrated and validated in real photobioreactors shown in Figures 2 and 3.

When modeling these types of processes, it is necessary to consider that the microalgae culture is composed of liquids, gases, and unicellular phototrophic microorganisms (which are considered as part of the liquid fraction of the system) and whose productivity depends on the conditions to which the culture cells are exposed, as described in Section III-B. Therefore, models based on the first principles should represent the main physicochemical and biological phenomena of the system, considering the relationships between light availability, culture conditions, photosynthesis rate, mass transfers, and mixtures between the liquid and gaseous state in the system. Therefore, these models should allow for the

description of the temporal and spatial behavior of the main process variables, such as the photosynthesis rate, biomass concentration, temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total inorganic carbon.

The models are developed equivalently for both types of reactors because the vast majority of physicochemical balances are very similar. In fact, if tubular and raceway photobioreactors are compared, both share the three basic design elements. First, they have the bubbling column or sump, for tubular or raceway, respectively, which are used for gas injection. Subsequently, they have the solar receiver, which is a closed tube in the case of the tubular reactors and a channel in the case of the raceway. Lastly, both have an impulsion system, which is a centrifugal pump for the tubular reactors and a paddle wheel for the raceway reactors. The mass transfer balances in the column or sump are considered as perfect mixing, while the balances in the case of the solar receiver (tube or channel) are represented as piston-flow by dividing this element into several sections and considering perfect mixing in each section. Finally, mass transfer phenomena occurring in the impulsion system are generally considered insignificant (due to their volume relative to the total reactor) and are therefore considered part of the sump or not taken into account in the model; although there are some works in which their effect has been analyzed for raceway reactors [17].

Considering these similarities, the following section summarizes the main balances of a model based on first principles using a raceway photobioreactor as a reference. During the presentation of the model, particularities based on one type of reactor or another will be indicated. Complete first-principles models for both photobioreactors can be found in [16], [17], [19], [20], [63].

A. First-principles models

The complete model of an industrial photobioreactor can be divided into three large blocks as described in Figure 6: the biological model that describes the growth rate of microalgae; the reactor engineering model, which describes the biological phenomena (biomass production, inorganic carbon consumption, etc.), mass transfer between the culture, and the atmosphere (such as exchanges of oxygen and carbon dioxide); and the thermal model, which describes the thermal balances along the reactor. In the reactors, these balances occur in the two main sections, the solar receiver and bubbling column in tubular reactors, and the channel and sump for raceway reactors. However, for the sake of simplicity, models will be presented considering the reactors as a single system using a perfect mixing approach. More detailed models describing the separated dynamics for the different parts of the reactors can be found in [16], [17], [63].

1) *Biological model:* The growth rate of a microalgae population is a measure of the increase in biomass over time, and it is an important way to express the relative ecological success of a species or strain in adapting to its natural environment or the experimental environment imposed on

Fig. 6: Full schematic photobioreactor model.

it. This rate is fundamentally related to photosynthesis and light availability based on culture conditions by normalized factors of the other variables. From this value, it is possible to calculate the microalgae biomass growth, oxygen production, and carbon consumption.

The microalgae-specific growth rate model has been extensively used in the literature [19], [64], [65], and its formulation depends on the different nutrient limitations that influence growth, as can be seen in [66]. Under conditions of excess nutrients, the most commonly used model states that the microalgae growth rate, μ , is made up of four factors that depend on photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and light availability inside the culture (I_{av}), and modified by the influence of temperature (T_w), pH, and dissolved oxygen (DO) on culture growth by the following expression:

$$\mu(t) = \mu(I_{av})(t) \cdot \bar{\mu}(T_w)(t) \cdot \bar{\mu}(pH)(t) \cdot \bar{\mu}(DO)(t) \quad (1)$$

The main limiting nutrient that is characteristic of microalgae is light. The equations relating the microalgae growth rate μ and solar irradiance I are called light limitation growth models. This influence has been characterized by various authors in the literature to describe the different profiles that microalgae strains can acquire [65], [67], [68], [69], [70], [71], [72]. In general, the incidence of solar irradiance on the culture does not occur in a homogeneous way, but some layers of the culture receive more light than others. To unify this phenomenon, Molina uses the term of light availability I_{av} in [69] to analyze the light-limited growth of microalgae throughout microalgae culture, expressed as follows:

$$\mu(I_{av})(t) = \left(\mu_{max} \cdot \left(\frac{I_{av}^n(t)}{I_k^n + I_{av}^n(t)} \right) \right) - m(t) \quad (2)$$

where μ_{max} [day^{-1}] is the maximum growth rate, I_{av} [$\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] is the light availability inside the reactor summarized by the average irradiance inside the culture, I_k [$\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] is the minimum light needed by the microalgae to achieve maximum photosynthesis, n [-] is a form parameter, and m [day^{-1}] is the respiration rate of microalgae.

For a specific geometry, the average irradiance I_{av} is a function of the light path inside the culture, the biomass concentration, and the extinction coefficient of the biomass. The specific growth rate hyperbolically increases with the average irradiance up to achieve the maximum specific growth rate μ_{max} for the selected strain. Whatever the microalgae strains, a fixed specific growth rate is achieved for any operational conditions, being higher or lower according to the optimal value of other cultures' parameters such as temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen among others. The average irradiance is expressed as follows:

$$I_{av}(t) = \frac{I_0(t)}{K_a \cdot X_{alg}(t) \cdot d(t)} \left(1 - e^{-K_a \cdot X_{alg}(t) \cdot d(t)} \right) \quad (3)$$

where I_0 [$\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] is the solar irradiance on a horizontal surface, K_a [$\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$] is the microalgae extinction coefficient, X_{alg} [g m^{-3}] is the microalgae biomass concentration, and d [m] is the culture depth in the reactor.

Microalgae, like plants, have two types of respiration: dark respiration and photorespiration. The term m , below, encompasses both respiration terms:

$$m(t) = m_{min} + \left(m_{max} \cdot \left(\frac{I_{av}^{n_{resp}}(t)}{I_{k_{resp}}^{n_{resp}} + I_{av}^{n_{resp}}(t)} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

where m_{min} [day^{-1}] represents the dark respiration rate and m_{max} [day^{-1}] represents the maximum photorespiration rate; $I_{k_{resp}}$ [$\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] is the maximum light needed by the microalgae to stop photosynthesis and start the respiration process and n_{resp} [-] is the form parameter for respiration.

The influence of temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen affecting microalgae growth in (1) are normalized factors whose values vary between 0 and 1. Therefore, when these three terms ($\bar{\mu}(T_w)$, $\bar{\mu}(pH)$ and $\bar{\mu}(DO)$) are optimal and have a value of 1, the specific growth rate only depends on solar radiation and would have the maximum possible value. However, if any of these terms is not optimal, it would have a direct negative impact on the growth rate. As for light limitation, the influence of these factors on microalgae growth is expressed by various authors [73], [74] and represents the microalgae limitation growth models for temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen.

The values of maximum (T_{max} , pH_{max} , DO_{max}), minimum (T_{min} , pH_{min}) and optimal (T_{opt} , pH_{opt}) are characteristics of the microalgae strain and determine the range where the conditions do not negatively affect the state of the microalgae, in addition to the culture temperature (T_w [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]), the pH of the culture (pH_w [-]) and the dissolved oxygen of the culture (DO_w [%]), respectively. Those terms are calculated according to the following expressions:

$$\bar{\mu}(T_w)(t) = \frac{(T_w(t) - T_{max}) \cdot (T_w(t) - T_{min})^2}{(T_{opt} - T_{min}) \cdot ((T_{opt} - T_{min}) \cdot (T_w(t) - T_{opt}) - (T_{opt} - T_{max}) \cdot (T_{opt} + T_{min} - 2 \cdot T_w(t)))} \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\mu}(pH_w)(t) = \frac{(pH_w(t) - pH_{max}) \cdot (pH_w(t) - pH_{min})^2}{(pH_{opt} - pH_{min}) \cdot ((pH_{opt} - pH_{min}) \cdot (pH_w(t) - pH_{opt}) - (pH_{opt} - pH_{max}) \cdot (pH_{opt} + pH_{min} - 2 \cdot pH_w(t)))} \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{\mu}(DO)(t) = 1 - \left(\frac{DO_w(t)}{DO_{max}} \right)^{m_{DO}} \quad (7)$$

where m_{DO} [-] is a form parameter.

Figure 7 shows the experimental and estimated results for microalgae biomass concentration with a raceway reactor. Biomass concentration is one of the primary variables in the first-principles model, calculated based on the estimated growth rate of microalgae, μ , as described in the following section. Experimental results were obtained through a custom sensor that measures biomass based on absorbance and fluorescence parameters.

Fig. 7: First-principles biological model validation.

In the figure, an excellent correlation is observed between the experimental values and the values estimated by the model, demonstrating the accuracy in estimating biomass growth rate and, overall, the model's validity in accurately predicting biomass concentration over time.

2) *Engineering model*: As mentioned previously, during reactor operation, the main variables measured to monitor the state of the microalgae production process are biomass concentration, dissolved oxygen, and pH. The engineering model represents the mass balances that allow for the estimation of the state variables related to the process. Consequently, to estimate these main measurements, it is necessary to calculate the following balances: the production volume in the reactor, the biomass concentration (where the growth rate depends on the biological model), the oxygen concentration in the reactor, dissolved inorganic carbon concentration (DIC), the carbon dioxide concentration, and the proton concentration, directly related to the pH value.

Volume

The main volume, Vol [m^3] changes in the reactor occur due to the addition of water during the dilution process, the harvesting of the culture, and volume loss due to evaporation:

$$\frac{dVol(t)}{dt} = Q_d(t) - Q_h(t) - E_r(t) \cdot w \cdot L \quad (8)$$

where Q_d [$m^3 s^{-1}$] is the dilution flow rate of water inlet, Q_h [$m^3 s^{-1}$] represents the harvest flow rate of water outlet, E_r [$m s^{-1}$] is the evaporation rate, w [m] defines the width of the reactor, and L [m] represents the length of the reactor.

Microalgae biomass concentration

Microalgae biomass concentration is the key variable in the production process, as the goal is to maintain an optimal concentration over time. This balance depends primarily on the growth rate (1), which is determined by the biological model and reactor conditions, as well as the cell death rate and volume changes in the reactor:

$$\frac{dX_{alg}(t)}{dt} = X_{alg}(t) \cdot \mu(t) - X_{alg}(t) \cdot r_d - \frac{Q_d(t)}{Vol(t)} \cdot X_{alg}(t) \quad (9)$$

where X_{alg} [$g m^{-3}$] represents the microalgae biomass concentration, μ [s^{-1}] is the growth rate calculated from the biological model (1), r_d [$g m^{-3}$] is the decay rate of microalgae, and Vol [m^3] is the total volume of the reactor.

Oxygen concentration

Oxygen is produced through photosynthesis during daylight hours and accumulates within the reactor. Aeration in the sump facilitates the release of dissolved oxygen into the atmosphere, with the mass transfer coefficient (Kl_{alO_2}) depending on the flow rate of the injected air, as well as the transfer occurring between the reactor surface and the atmosphere ($Kl_{alO_{2atm}}$):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dX_{[O_2]}(t)}{dt} = & \frac{Q_d(t)}{Vol(t)} \cdot (X_{[O_2]^*}(t) - X_{[O_2]}(t)) + \\ & + X_{alg}(t) \cdot \mu(t) \cdot Y_{O_2/alg} \cdot \frac{1}{M_{O_2}} + \\ & + Kl_{alO_2} \cdot (X_{[O_2]_{air}}(t) - X_{[O_2]}(t)) \cdot \frac{Vol_{sump}}{Vol(t)} + \\ & + K_{O_2} \cdot Kl_{alCO_2} \cdot (X_{[O_2]_{CO_2}}(t) - X_{[O_2]}(t)) \cdot \frac{Vol_{sump}}{Vol(t)} + \\ & + Kl_{alO_{2atm}} \cdot (X_{[O_2]^*}(t) - X_{[O_2]}(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $X_{[O_2]^*}$ [$mol m^{-3}$] represents the oxygen equilibrium concentration in the atmosphere (according to Henry's law), $Y_{O_2/alg}$ [$g_{O_2} g_{algae}^{-1}$] denotes the yield of oxygen production by microalgae, M_{O_2} [$mol g^{-1}$] is the molar mass of oxygen, Kl_{alO_2} [s^{-1}] is the volumetric gas-liquid mass transfer coefficient for air in the sump, $X_{[O_2]_{air}}$ [$mol m^{-3}$] represents the oxygen concentration of the air injected into the sump, Vol_{sump} [m^3] denotes the volume of the sump where air is injected, K_{O_2} [-] is the transfer coefficient constant for oxygen, Kl_{alCO_2} [s^{-1}] is the volumetric gas-liquid mass transfer coefficient for CO_2 in the sump, $X_{[O_2]_{CO_2}}$ [$mol m^{-3}$] is the oxygen concentration when CO_2 is injected in the sump, and $Kl_{alO_{2atm}}$ [s^{-1}] is the volumetric mass transfer coefficient for air exchange with the atmosphere.

Regarding the mass transfer resulting from gas injection into the sump (either O_2 or CO_2), it depends on the volumetric gas-liquid mass transfer coefficient (Kl_{alx} , with $x = \{O_2, CO_2\}$), that it is determined due to sump geometry and size of the plate diffusers, and the driving force at each section. The driving force is determined by the concentration of the component in the liquid phase and its equilibrium with the gas phase in contact, as follows:

$$Kl_{al,x}(t) = \alpha \cdot \epsilon^\beta$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{Q_{gas}(t)}{Q_{gas}(t) + Q_l(t)}, \quad Q_l(t) = w \cdot d(t) \cdot V_l(t) \quad (11)$$

where α and β are experimental coefficients associated with sump geometry and mass transfer capacity, Q_{gas} [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] represents the injected gas flow rate, Q_l [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] is the volumetric liquid flow rate in the reactor, d [m] is the culture depth, and V_l [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] denotes the liquid velocity in the reactor.

Dissolved Inorganic Carbon

To calculate the pH of the system, it is essential to first establish a balance of dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), as this forms the basis for the carbon dioxide and proton balances within the system. The DIC balance allows for the estimation of changes in inorganic carbon concentration, which are influenced by several key factors: the system's inlet flow rate, CO_2 consumption by microalgae during photosynthesis, mass transfer due to CO_2 and air injection into the reactor, and CO_2 transfer to the atmosphere. These factors determine the dynamics of inorganic carbon within the system, ultimately affecting the acid-base equilibrium, which is crucial for calculating pH:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dX_{DIC}(t)}{dt} = & \frac{Q_d(t)}{Vol(t)} \cdot (X_{DIC_{inlet}}(t) - X_{DIC}(t)) - \\ & - X_{alg}(t) \cdot \mu(t) \cdot Y_{CO_2/alg} \cdot \frac{1}{M_{CO_2}} + \\ & + Kl_{alCO_2} \cdot (X_{[CO_2]_{gas}}(t) - X_{[CO_2]}(t)) \cdot \frac{Vol_{sump}}{Vol(t)} + \\ & + K_{CO_2} \cdot Kl_{alO_2} \cdot (X_{[CO_2]_{air}}(t) - X_{[CO_2]}(t)) \cdot \frac{Vol_{sump}}{Vol(t)} + \\ & + Kl_{alCO_2_{atm}} \cdot (X_{[CO_2]^*}(t) - X_{[CO_2]}(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $X_{DIC_{inlet}}$ [mol m^{-3}] represents the DIC inlet during the dilution process, $Y_{CO_2/alg}$ [$\text{gO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}_{algae}$] denotes the yield of CO_2 consumption by microalgae, $X_{[CO_2]}$ [mol g^{-1}] is the molar mass of carbon dioxide, $X_{[CO_2]_{gas}}$ [mol m^{-3}] represents the CO_2 concentration of the gas injected into the sump, Vol_{sump} [m^3] denotes the volume of the sump where CO_2 is injected, K_{CO_2} [-] is the transfer coefficient constant for carbon dioxide, $X_{[CO_2]_{air}}$ [mol m^{-3}] is the CO_2 concentration when air is injected in the sump, $Kl_{alCO_2_{atm}}$ [s^{-1}] is the volumetric mass transfer coefficient for CO_2 exchange with the atmosphere, and $X_{[CO_2]^*}$ [mol m^{-3}] represents the CO_2 equilibrium concentration in the atmosphere (according to Henry's law).

Carbon dioxide and proton concentration

The carbon dioxide balance is essential for understanding carbon dynamics within the system, as CO_2 participates in both atmospheric exchange and microalgae consumption through photosynthesis.

Meanwhile, the balance of the proton concentration ($X_{[H^+]}$) is crucial to determine the acid-base status of the

system, as the proton concentration defines the pH, expressed as $pH = -\log_{10}(X_{[H^+]})$. This balance considers processes that generate or consume protons, such as the dissociation of CO_2 into carbon species (bicarbonate and carbonate) and the autoionization of water. Changes in $X_{[H^+]}$ concentration are directly related to carbon chemistry within the system, and an accurate proton balance enables a precise calculation of pH, a key parameter for the stability and efficiency of the biological process:

$$\frac{dX_{[CO_2]}(t)}{dt} = \frac{dX_{DIC}(t)}{dt} \cdot \frac{P_2 - X_{[CO_2]}(t) \cdot P_1 \cdot P_3}{P_2} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{dX_{[H^+]}(t)}{dt} = P_3 \cdot \frac{dX_{[CO_2]}(t)}{dt} \quad (14)$$

where P_1 , P_2 , and P_3 are groups of terms that depend on the concentration of $X_{[H^+]}$, $X_{[CO_2]}$, the dissociation constants of carbon (K_1 and K_2), and the autoionization constant of water (K_w):

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 = & \frac{K_1}{X_{[H^+]}^2(t)} + \frac{2 \cdot K_1 \cdot K_2}{X_{[H^+]}^3(t)} \\ P_2 = & 1 + \frac{K_1}{X_{[H^+]}(t)} + \frac{K_1 \cdot K_2}{X_{[H^+]}^2(t)} \\ P_3 = & \frac{\frac{K_1}{X_{[H^+]}(t)} + \frac{2 \cdot K_1 \cdot K_2}{X_{[H^+]}^2(t)}}{1 + \frac{K_w}{X_{[H^+]}^2(t)} + \frac{K_1 \cdot X_{[CO_2]}(t)}{X_{[H^+]}^2(t)} + \frac{4 \cdot X_{[CO_2]}(t) \cdot K_1 \cdot K_2}{X_{[H^+]}^3(t)}} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Figure 8 presents an example of the engineering model validation for data collected in the reactors from Figure 3. The dissolved oxygen signal in the medium is depicted, along with the airflow rate signal injected, which directly influences the oxygen dynamics in the system. The effect of air injection during nighttime is clearly visible, where increased oxygen availability corresponds to an increase in the injected airflow rate. The figure shows that the model accurately captures the trends in dissolved oxygen signal in response to changes in airflow.

Fig. 8: First-principles engineering model validation.

Furthermore, this figure includes validation data for pH, where similar trends are observed, reflecting the characteristic changes of the system and demonstrating the effectiveness of the model in capturing pH variations.

3) *Thermal model*: The culture temperature is calculated from the thermal balance in the reactor in such a way that the culture temperature can be estimated from environmental input variables such as solar irradiance, ambient temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed. The implemented temperature model was previously validated in real outdoor conditions for a whole year and presented in [18]. The evolution of culture temperature can be described as follows:

$$\frac{dT_w(t)}{dt} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{accumulated}}{Vol(t) \cdot C_p \cdot \rho} - \frac{Q_d \cdot T_{inlet}(t)}{Vol(t)} + \frac{Q_h \cdot T_w(t)}{Vol(t)} + \frac{E_r(t) \cdot T_w(t)}{Vol(t)} \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{accumulated} = \dot{Q}_{irradiance} + \dot{Q}_{radiation} + \dot{Q}_{evaporation} + \dot{Q}_{convection} + \dot{Q}_{conduction} + \dot{Q}_{dilution} - \dot{Q}_{harvest}$$

where T_w [°C] is the temperature of the culture in the reactor, Vol [m] represents the culture volume, A [m²] is the surface of the reactor, C_p [J kg⁻¹ °C⁻¹] is the specific heat capacity of the culture, ρ [kg m⁻³] is the density of the culture $\dot{Q}_{accumulation}$ [W] represents the heat flow accumulated in the reactor, Q_d [m³ s⁻¹] is the water flow for the dilution process, Q_h [m³ s⁻¹] is the culture flow for the harvesting process, $\dot{Q}_{irradiance}$ [W] represents the heat flow from sunlight, $\dot{Q}_{radiation}$ [W] is the heat flow from long-wave radiation, $\dot{Q}_{evaporation}$ [W] shows the heat flow produced by the evaporation process in the reactor, $\dot{Q}_{convection}$ [W] is the heat flow caused by convection, $\dot{Q}_{conduction}$ [W] represents the heat flow between the reactor and the layer under it through the conduction process, $\dot{Q}_{dilution}$ [W] is the heat that is added when the fresh medium is supplied to the reactor, and $\dot{Q}_{harvest}$ [W] is the heat that is subtracted when culture is removed from the reactor during the harvesting process.

Figure 9 shows a validation example of temperature data for the thermal first-principle model. Both experimental and estimated temperature signals show a high degree of similarity, indicating that the model accurately reproduces temperature variations [18]. Furthermore, this figure represents the environmental variables that serve as inputs to the mathematical model, including external factors that can influence the conditions of the system. The accuracy in predicting temperature highlights the model's ability to effectively integrate the influence of these environmental variables, enhancing the system's reliability in estimating the culture temperature.

B. Data-based models

As presented in the previous section, modeling these systems is not a straightforward task. First-principles models are very useful for process understanding, the development of system simulators or digital twins, and for optimization control purposes [56], [75], [76]. However, they can be too complex and time consuming to develop and calibrate. In this sense, data-driven models offer a simpler solution to obtain

Fig. 9: First-principles thermal model validation

linear and nonlinear models that can be used for control design purposes. For example, in [22], [36], [77], [78], and [79], different data-driven models are presented to capture the pH dynamics. In [36], a first-order model plus time delay was obtained to capture the pH dynamics with respect to CO₂ injections and solar radiation variations (expressed here in the Laplace transform domain):

$$pH(s) = \underbrace{\frac{k_1}{1 + \tau_1 s}}_{TF_1(s)} \underbrace{\frac{w_n^2}{s^2 + 2\delta w_n s + w_n^2} e^{-t_r s}}_{TF_2(s)} q(s) + \underbrace{\frac{k_r}{1 + \tau_r s}}_{TF_3(s)} I(s) \quad (17)$$

where pH is the pH of the culture, q is the CO₂ flow rate and I is the global radiation. As can be seen, the dynamics of pH with respect to CO₂ is given by a first-order term, TF_1 , which marks the dominant dynamics of the process, together with a second-order transfer function, TF_2 , which represents the oscillations existing in the system due to CO₂ injections that are attenuated by the recirculation of the medium along the solar receiver. Subsequently, the transfer function TF_3 represents the overdamped effect of solar radiation on pH as an indirect effect of the photosynthesis process. In the above equation, k_1 and k_r are the static gains of the transfer functions TF_1 and TF_3 , τ_1 and τ_r the time constants of these transfer functions, and t_r the time delay between CO₂ flow rate and pH. Finally, δ and w_n represent the relative damping coefficient and the undamped natural frequency for the oscillatory term TF_2 . These parameters take particular values depending on the type of reactor, the type of microalgae strain and the season of the year. This simplified model presents the same structure in both open and closed reactors and has been correctly validated experimentally in both types of system [34], [42], [47], [77].

On the other hand, in [22], a new data-driven model was developed to estimate and predict pH dynamics in freshwater raceway photobioreactors. The model was trained with 10 months of data and validated along the different seasons with an accuracy over 80%. The resulting model is based purely on data measured from the reactor and divides the pH dynamics into two different behaviors. One behavior is described by the variation in pH due to the photosynthesis phenomena caused by microalgae called *free response*; and the other comes from the effect of CO₂ injections into the

medium for control purposes called *forced response*.

The proposed resulting model is shown in Equation (18), where F_1 represents the forced response influenced by CO_2 injections and F_2 the free response.

$$pH(t) = \begin{cases} F_1(t, CO_2, I, T_w, h), & CO_2 > 0 \\ F_2(t, I, DO, T_w, h), & CO_2 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

As observed in Equation (18), F_1 depends on time (t), injection of CO_2 flow rate (CO_2), solar radiation (I), culture temperature (T_w) and medium level (h). On the other hand, F_2 depends on time, solar radiation, culture temperature, medium level, and dissolved oxygen (DO) in the medium. Notice that F_2 depends on DO , as it is a direct indicator of how microalgae make the photosynthesis process and thus affect the pH rise.

The forced response, F_1 , can be modeled as a first-order transfer function, represented as the following differential equation:

$$F_1 \Rightarrow \tau(I, T_w, h) \frac{dpH(t)}{dt} + pH(t) = k(I, T_w, h) \cdot CO_2(t - t_d) \quad (19)$$

where pH is the measured pH at the end of the channel, CO_2 is the gas flow injected at the bottom of the sump, k is the static gain of the system, τ is the system time constant and t_d is the time delay. The pH free response will be modelled with the following expression:

$$F_2 \Rightarrow \frac{dpH(t)}{dt} = \alpha(I, DO, T_w, h) \cdot pH(t) \quad (20)$$

where pH represents the evolution of pH and α determines the slope with which the pH increases due to the photosynthesis effect. As the rate of increase of pH will depend on photosynthetic activity, this last parameter will depend on solar radiation, culture temperature, medium level, and dissolved oxygen in the medium [22]. This model was used to design an adaptive control algorithm approach, such as will be described in next section.

On the other hand, in [77], [78], [79], and [80] linear and nonlinear solutions were developed based on ARX, NARX, Wiener, and neural networks models allowing to capture the nonlinearities of pH dynamics. Some of these models were used for the design of nonlinear control approaches in [43] and [78] obtaining satisfactory results.

V. CONTROL PROBLEMS

As in any industrial system, the optimization of large-scale microalgae-based processes requires achieving a near-optimal environment for microalgae to grow, multiply, and maximize biomass production. This includes providing the right concentration of nutrients to the culture, removing toxic metabolic products, and controlling important internal cellular parameters. On the other hand, an analysis of the effect of optimizing key process parameters on biomass production and wastewater treatment costs is also required. This can be reached by evaluating the balance between the energy requested to maintain optimal microalgae growth, injected CO_2 , and the costs recovered through the derived

products. Therefore, different control objectives can be established. High-level ones characterized by slow dynamics can be found for high-quality biomass, productivity, microalgae growth prediction, cost reductions, water treatment capacity, and/or CO_2 mitigation. In addition, low-level objectives with fast-dynamics variables (e.g. pH, dissolved oxygen, temperature) must be reached to fulfill the high-level requirements and obtain an adequate balance in the bacterial metabolisms and biomass production. Therefore, hierarchical Real-Time Optimization (RTO) control schemes, as that presented in Figure 10, are highly recommended to achieve these control objectives. Long-term economic objectives are considered in the high-level layers to maximize incomes and reduce costs. These objectives are converted into short-term goals to maximize biomass production, which directly affects the regulatory or low-level layer to control the running process variables in the daily reactor operation.

Fig. 10: General hierarchical control structure for microalgae production systems.

A general analysis of the global control problem can be obtained as follows. The supplies necessary for the operation of the process are the CO_2 required both for photosynthesis and to control the pH, air injection to control the dissolved oxygen, and nutrients supplied during dilution. The rest of the requirements of the microalgae for their growth are acquired directly from their environment at no cost. These costs are directly proportional to the volume of CO_2 and air injected, and the volume of water introduced to the reactor, assuming that the concentration of nutrients in the dilution water (freshwater plus nutrients or wastewater) is always the same and its cost is time-invariant. If the CO_2 used came from another industrial activity, it can be represented as income rather than a cost due to the positive effect of reducing the carbon footprint.

The energy costs of the process are mainly associated with the blower in charge of air bubbling, the post-processing of the harvested medium, and the paddle-wheel in charge of driving the fluid. Usually, fixed costs are not represented in the cost functions of the optimizers, and the energy cost of

the paddle wheel may seem so. However, the optimizer's ability to increase or decrease the medium level affects the power demanded by the paddle wheel to maintain a constant fluid velocity, and thus the energy cost of the problem. This cost increases proportionally to the square of the water level. On the other hand, the cost of the blower will be related to the volume of air bubbled, while the cost of post-processing will be related to the amount of medium harvested. The price of electricity can be assumed to be constant, although its variation throughout the day could affect the optimization result. Profit from the product can be understood in two different ways. It can be considered the yield due to the biomass harvested, thus taking into account the revenue at the time it is collected; or it can be considered the yield due to the biomass generated inside the reactor, under the assumption that, once produced, the biomass will be harvested sooner or later, obtaining that same yield. Furthermore, when microalgae production is combined with wastewater treatment, water treatment capacity can be considered as an additional or main objective in the cost function. In this case, microalgae and bacteria grow in the system simultaneously, and when water treatment capacity is the main goal, the optimization problem must focus on providing optimal values of pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen for the bacteria population. Notice that when microalgae are produced using wastewater, the optimization problem can be understood as a multi-objective control problem, as the optimal solution can be focused on maximizing microalgae production (using wastewater only as nutrients supply), or maximizing the water treatment capacity (using microalgae to provide oxygen to the bacteria and uptake nutrients from the media), or to obtain a balance between these two objectives.

In this tutorial, as an example, the optimization problem will focus on maximizing microalgae production using freshwater plus nutrients, where the optimization and regulatory layers will be described.

1) *Optimization layer*: Such as presented in Figure 10, the optimization layer is in charge of minimizing the given optimization criterion and calculating the setpoints of the different process variables that allow the system to operate properly and achieve the optimization objective. This task can be carried out using different control methods, such as Economic MPC (EMPC), RTO, etc. In this work, two solutions are shown as examples based on a static RTO for microalgae production in raceway reactors and a dynamic RTO for microalgae production in tubular reactors.

Figure 11 shows a hierarchical control structure to optimize microalgae production in raceway reactors using a static RTO strategy that focuses on estimating the optimal steady state of the system every hour. This steady state is described in terms of setpoints of water level, biomass concentration, pH, and dissolved oxygen, which will be reached using PID controllers [53]. The proposed cost function J [€/s] to be minimized is given by the following equation:

$$J = -P_b \cdot X_{alg} \cdot Vol \cdot \mu + C_{CO_2} \cdot Q_{CO_2} + C_d \cdot Q_d + C_{air} \cdot Q_{air} + C_{pw} \cdot d^2 \quad (21)$$

where fixed costs of the process are not considered. The cost includes the CO₂ flow rate (due to the cost of gas), the dilution flow rate (due to the cost of nutrients added to the dilution water) and the air flow rate (due to the energy consumption of the air blower). There will also be a cost associated with the water level, since the paddle wheel is in charge of driving the medium at a constant speed and thus the power consumed by it will be proportional to the driven water volume. The yield term (first negative term) represents the profit associated with the biomass produced. The total biomass [kg] is $B(t) = X_{alg}(t) \cdot Vol(t)$, which is given by $\frac{dB(t)}{dt} = X_{alg}(t) \cdot \mu(t) \cdot Vol(t)$. Thus, in the final cost function defined in Equation (21), P_b is the price of biomass considering post-processing costs, C_{CO_2} is the cost per liter of CO₂, C_d the cost of nutrients in a liter of dilution water, C_{air} is the cost of blower electricity per liter of air, and C_{pw} the cost associated with the paddle wheel.

Fig. 11: Hierarchical RTO control structure [53].

The optimizer is implemented using a receding horizon approach and considers the median value of solar irradiance and ambient temperature over the next hour, as well as the current value of ground temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed, to optimize the proposed function. Since this is a static optimization, the optimizer will return the setpoints of biomass concentration, water level, pH, and dissolved oxygen that optimize the proposed cost function, using PID controllers to reach these references.

Figures 12 and 13 show the results of using the proposed strategy for data from October 25-29, 2023. It is important to mention that the variables are not controlled during the night, as there is no light, and thus microalgae do not grow.

It can be seen how the optimizer behaves as expected. First, the pH is driven to its optimum value throughout the simulation, which is 8. The controller with a flow rate of CO₂ takes care of keeping this variable at its reference despite changes in radiation. For dissolved oxygen, the optimal value is not excessively high, but it does not lead to very large air injections, thus preserving a high specific growth rate without too much cost.

The most interesting variables are the water level and the biomass concentration [81]. The level is kept to a minimum (5 cm) during most of the test, due to the costs associated

Fig. 12: Simulation results for the static RTO in raceway reactors. In red, the optimal setpoints and in blue the simulated value. Dashed vertical lines mark the beginning and end of the optimization each day.

Fig. 13: Manipulated variables corresponding to Figure 12.

with the paddle wheel, as mentioned above. On the other hand, biomass concentration has a very variable setpoint, since, as previously discussed, its optimum value varies with the global irradiance. This is why, at the central hours of the day, its setpoint is generally higher. Likewise, the third day, which presents much lower setpoints, also has significantly lower irradiance. Dilution and harvesting typically take place at the end of the day, corresponding to the lowest radiation hours, as expected.

Fig. 14: Hierarchical control scheme for biomass optimization in tubular reactors [52].

A different approach can be used with a dynamic RTO, such as presented in [52] for tubular reactors. In this case, the RTO layer uses the nonlinear dynamic model of the system and the controllers of the lower layer such as presented in Figure 14. In this way, the optimizer considers the resulting behaviour of the system when imposing certain setpoints, on the basis of which it will compute the cost function. This solution only uses pH controls in the lower layer when a PI controller plus feedforward was implemented. The cost function was the following:

$$J = V_{bio}\hat{X}_{bio} - V_{cost}W_{CO_2} - V_{env}\hat{L}_{CO_2} \quad (22)$$

where X_{bio} is the estimated biomass productivity, W_{CO_2} is the total mass of CO_2 used to control pH, and L_{CO_2} are the predicted CO_2 losses generated by CO_2 inputs to the medium. On the other hand, V_{bio} , V_{cost} and V_{env} are the prices associated with biomass production, CO_2 injection, and environmental CO_2 losses, respectively. Details on the cost function and its relationship to system models can be found in [52]. This solution was experimentally evaluated in 15000 L tubular reactors where it was necessary to achieve levels of biomass production similar to a single control architecture where constant pH setpoints are used throughout the day, but with a 10% reduction in production costs and environmental pollution. Figure 15 shows an example of an experimental result in which it is possible to observe how the pH setpoint is modified throughout the day according to the optimization results of the upper layer.

Fig. 15: Experimental result of the dynamic RTO approach in tubular reactors [52].

2) *Regulatory layer*: As described above, the outputs of the optimization layer are the setpoints for the low-level control variables, mainly pH, dissolved oxygen, and temperature. All of them, together with the availability of light, have a direct effect on the growth rate of microalgae, as shown in Equation (1). Therefore, it is important to keep them close to the optimal values calculated by the optimization layer in order to contribute to the maximization of the optimization criteria.

Among all these variables, pH is the most difficult variable to control due to its changing dynamics and has a high impact on microalgae growth rate [57]. The pH is modified by injections of CO_2 as mentioned above, which, in turn, are used as a carbon input to the medium. The evolution of pH in the medium is influenced by two phenomena: CO_2 input and

CO₂ consumption as a function of sunlight availability. Injections of CO₂ contribute to the formation of carbonic acid, which causes a decrease in the pH of the medium. On the other hand, when microalgae carry out photosynthesis in the presence of solar radiation, they consume CO₂ and produce oxygen, causing a gradual increase in pH. In addition, when variations in solar radiation occur, for example as a result of passing clouds, there are also variations in the photosynthesis rate and therefore a corresponding effect on the rate of change in pH. Thus, the pH control problem has CO₂ flow injection as the control signal, pH as the controlled variable, and solar radiation as the main disturbance. It should be noted that this is a control problem with changing dynamics in which the time constants of the process are associated with the current state of the strain and the weather conditions [22].

On the basis of these characteristics, the problem of pH control has aroused great interest in the scientific community, and there are numerous results for both open and closed photobioreactors. It is possible to find solutions based on the on/off control [82], PID control [34], MPC [36], [83], sliding mode control [41], event-based control [40], [84], robust control [85], control with active disturbance rejection [86], and learning MPC [42]. Recently, an adaptive PID control algorithm was developed based on data-driven techniques using the model presented in Equation (18), where the pH model parameters, and consequently those of the controller, were adapted based on weather conditions and reactor operation variables. The resulting algorithm was experimentally tested under different weather conditions, providing satisfactory results. Figure 16 shows an experimental result in which it can be observed how the model parameters change their values due to the decision trees estimation using the data-driven model described in Section IV-B. It can be seen that the decision tree model is capable of adjusting the controller and achieving a successful pH regulation (note that the pH control is performed between 9am and 20pm according to the solar radiation availability). The adjustment of the model parameters through the day caused by the different combinations of the instantaneous values of the predictors can also be observed.

Fig. 16: Experimental results of pH control [22].

Dissolved oxygen is another of the fast dynamic variables that significantly affect the rate of photosynthesis and consequently the amount of final product obtained. The control of dissolved oxygen has not been studied as extensively in the literature as in the case of pH, and even today it is still an important field of research despite existing advances. The problem of oxygen accumulation is more prominent in closed photobioreactors as there is no release of oxygen to the outside. In the case of open reactors, its regulation was generally not contemplated since it was considered that excess of dissolved oxygen was automatically eliminated to the atmosphere. However, in practice, this statement has been proven to be incorrect and dissolved oxygen concentrations higher than 500% of saturation have been observed [45], [62]. Therefore, for both types of photobioreactors, installation of aeration systems is required to reduce the amount of accumulated oxygen. The control problem consists of ensuring that the oxygen concentration does not exceed a certain threshold, above which the photosynthesis rate is exponentially reduced, even reaching zero values for dissolved oxygen values above saturation 350%. Thus, existing control strategies are based on the use of on/off controllers that activate the injection of constant air flow when the concentration of dissolved oxygen exceeds the established reference value and disconnect it otherwise [45]. The main problem with this method is the large amount of energy required to bring compressed air into the photobioreactor at a constant flow rate, which is of great importance in the case of open reactors, where it is necessary to maintain low production costs to be competitive in the market.

Due to this problem of consumption and excess aeration, the development of control strategies is therefore required to provide a feasible solution from an energetic point of view. In this sense, it was recently demonstrated in [87] that the dissolved oxygen mass transfer coefficient in the sump of a raceway photobioreactor is not constant throughout the day, and it is possible to relate its variability to the air flow rate applied to the system. As a result, a model was obtained to estimate the online mass transfer coefficient, which was used to design a new control strategy capable of determining the air flow rate required by the system at each instant of time according to the established dissolved oxygen threshold [48]. This new strategy was implemented under real outdoor conditions in a raceway reactor of 80 m² to control dissolved oxygen accumulation and to reduce air injections. Figure 17 shows the experimental results for two consecutive days. As observed, the proposed strategy was able to reach the required setpoint values despite solar radiation changes. It can also be shown that the variation in the mass transfer coefficient implies a variable air injection gas flow, reducing the energy cost compared to classical solutions [48].

Finally, in terms of temperature control as a fast dynamic variable that affects microalgae production, it should be noted that in the case of tubular photobioreactors this control is carried out using heat exchangers located inside the bubbling column [88]. In this sense, the control loops used are based on classical heat exchanger control solutions, and there

Fig. 17: Experimental results of dissolved oxygen control.

are no relevant contributions in this respect. However, in the case of the raceway photobioreactor, temperature control is usually not carried out because of the high costs involved. In recent years, and due to advances in temperature models of this type of reactors presented in Section IV-A [18], an optimization algorithm has been developed that allows regulating the culture temperature by varying the depth of the medium along the reactor channel. This contribution is presented as a promising solution in this field [89], [90], [91].

VI. MONITORING AND SUPERVISION

As described in the previous section, hierarchical control approaches can greatly contribute to optimize microalgae production. Those optimal conditions are associated with the specific microalgae strain to be produced in the reactors, as the biomass of each strain has particular properties for the production of biofuels, high-value pigments, pharmaceuticals, or nutritional supplements. For that reason, for these applications to be economically viable and scalable, the ability to accurately monitor, identify, and classify microalgal species is critical. This classification is particularly important for ensuring that the selected strains possess the optimal characteristics for pigment production, growth rate, and resilience to environmental conditions.

This classification and monitoring task has traditionally been performed manually by qualified laboratory personnel using a microscope. This approach relies on the observation of key morphological traits, such as cell size, shape, pigmentation, and colony structure, to identify different species. While this method is reliable for well-documented and morphologically distinct species, it faces significant limitations when dealing with species that exhibit subtle morphological differences or when identifying strains that may vary under different environmental conditions. The laborious nature of traditional microscopy-based classification becomes particularly problematic in industrial-scale operations, where continuous monitoring of the culture is necessary to maintain optimal growth and production conditions. The time and expertise required for manual identification introduce bottlenecks into the production process. Moreover, open raceway reactors are especially prone to species mixing and contamination, increasing the need for frequent and rapid classification. Thus, the limitations of traditional

methods make them inadequate for the demands of large-scale microalgal production. This creates a pressing need for more advanced and automated solutions that can deliver the required precision and speed in classifying microalgal species under industrial conditions.

Recently, different methods for approaching the classification of microalgae cultures based on machine learning and, more specifically artificial neural networks, have been developed. This set of techniques uses descriptive data from the culture, such as microscopic images, spectral sweeps, and cytometries, to extract information that often transcends human perception. In this way, they are able to infer hidden patterns in the data, learning from these in an automatic way to develop models that allow their characterization. The techniques presented offer high classification accuracy, replacing the need for manual and slow methods with fast and easy-to-apply approaches.

Image-based microalgae classification models have shown great utility in the literature [92], [93], being suitable for large and diverse datasets, providing high accuracy and being applicable for classification of mixtures. For instance, a convolutional neural network was developed in [21] to classify 6 different genera of microalgae, where different species of each genus were used to train the model. In this work, more than 3 million of images were collected from multiple species of each of the genera. The model developed was based on *AlexNet*, applying transfer learning on the last layers to adapt it to the problem faced. The concept of classification thresholds was employed, studying its effect on model accuracy and dataset size. When faced with the test set, the original model achieved an average prediction of 83%. With a classification threshold of 0.5, this value increases to 88%. More demanding thresholds can increase prediction to 99%. The procedures followed in this work are shown in Figure 18.

Fig. 18: Flow chart of the microalgae classification model using images developed in [21].

In addition to image-based models, there are also models in the literature that make use of sequence data to classify different genera of microalgae. The sequential data used

for this type of models are spectral sweeps of cultures, such sweeps can come from hyperspectral imaging, optical absorbance spectrophotometers, or fluorescence spectrophotometers [54], [94]. The data sequence used in this type of model depends on the instrumentation used in the acquisition process. In the case of hyperspectral cameras or optical absorbance spectrophotometers, the information obtained contains a sequence of absorbance or transmittance values at different wavelengths, allowing the detection of biochemical compounds that absorb at that wavelength, and which are found in different proportions depending on the genus. Similarly, fluorescence spectrophotometers collect the fluorescence values emitted by the sample at different excitation wavelength values of the sample.

For instance, in [54], a spectrophotometer was used to make sweeping in the visible spectrum and 1D convolutional networks to classify 4 genera of microalgae with an average F1 score of 96.43%. The resulting model shows the ability to detect contamination of pure samples by analysing the output of the *Softmax* layer [54]. This work shows not only laboratory results, but also samples from 3 different reactors at the facilities of the IFAPA research center. Figure 19 summarizes the main steps of the proposed solution.

Fig. 19: Flow chart of the microalgae classification model using spectrometry developed in [54].

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has introduced microalgae production as a topic of industrial significance, presenting it as a robust and sustainable approach to addressing various societal challenges. Microalgae, in particular, provide a variety of benefits to reduce environmental impact, mitigate CO₂ emissions, transform and recycle waste, treat wastewater, and generate alternative energy sources.

However, implementing these processes at an industrial scale, especially under outdoor conditions, involves considerable complexity. This has led to various areas of research focused on photobioreactor design, mass transfer phenomena analysis, examination of light/dark cycles in photosynthesis, biological and structural modeling, controlling key variables, and optimizing the overall production system.

As outlined in the paper, modeling and control techniques are vital to enhancing these systems. Nevertheless, there

are significant differences between developing solutions for laboratory-scale reactors with stable, semi-controlled conditions, and those intended for industrial-scale and outdoor environments, as explored in this study. Notably, outdoor operations expose the system to yearly variations influenced by environmental conditions specific to the photobioreactor's location, daily changes due to solar cycles and passing clouds, and internal production variations caused by light and nutrient gradients within the reactor. These changing and uncertain behaviors pose very interesting challenges for the development of modeling, control, and optimization solutions to account for these problems in the microalgae industry.

The research findings summarized here have been gradually developed and achieved over years as a result of a close collaboration between the University of Almería with numerous national and international partnerships from industry and academy.

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